

DETERMINATION OF URANIUM USING DISODIUM 1:8-DIHYDROXY-NAPHTHALENE-3:6-DISULPHONATE (CHROMOTROPIC SALT) AS A COLORIMETRIC REAGENT

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The use of disodium 1:8-dihydroxynaphthalene-3:6-disulphonate (chromotropic salt) as a reagent for the determination of uranium on a micro-scale has been described. The reagent is sensitive to 30 p.p.m. of uranium and Beer's law holds good in the range of concentration of 50-200 p.p.m. The reagent added should be at least 30 times the molar concentration of uranium. The pH of the medium should be adjusted at 4.00 ± 0.50 . For the determination, either a photoelectric colorimeter with a blue filter or a spectrophotometer can be employed. The interference of various cations and anions has also been studied. The chelate has a composition of 1:1 of the reactants.

The determination of uranium on a micro-scale has become an important problem in recent years. Various organic compounds have been suggested as colorimetric reagents, e. g., dibenzoylmethane (Yoe *et al.*, *Anal. Chem.*, 1953, 25, 1200), salicylic acid (Müller, *Chem. Ztg.*, 1919, 43, 739) and sulphosalicylic acid (Rodden, "Analytical Chemistry of the Manhattan Project, McGraw Hill Book Co. Inc., New York, 1950). Rây *et al.* (this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 491) studied the application of salicylamide in the colorimetric estimation of uranium and discussed the relative merits of the common colorimetric procedures of uranium (cf. Rây *et al.*, *Proc. Ind. Sci. Cong.*, 1954, 40, Part III, p. 48). Rây and Bandyopadhyaya (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 21) observed that salicylamidoxime yielded an orange-red complex with uranyl salts and Bandyopadhyaya (*ibid.*, 1956, 33, 269) employed the spectrophotometric method for working out the details of the use of this reagent in the micro-determination of uranium. The latter author also noted the interference of various common ions on the sensitivity of the colour formation.

In recent communications from this laboratory, a detailed search has been reported for new colorimetric reagents in inorganic analysis. Mukherji and Dey tried Alizarin Red S (this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 461; *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1957, 26A, 20), Aluminon (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1956, 182, 424), rhodizonic acid (*Chim. Anal.*, 1957, 39, 148) and Quinalizarin (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1957, 154, 347) and suggested further applications of these reagents in colorimetric analysis. They also examined the possibility of using these reagents for the spectrophotometric determination of uranium on a micro-scale (Mukherji and Dey, *Proc. Ind. Sci. Cong.*, 1957, 44, Part III, p. 70).

Disodium 1:8-dihydroxynaphthalene-3:6-disulphonate (chromotropic salt) is known to yield coloured lakes with various metals. Mathur and Dey (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1957, 154, 347) have recently reported the reagent to be very sensitive to $Hg-Hg^{II}$, Su^{IV} , Au^{III} , Mo^{VI} , Fe^{III} and UO_2^{VI} as well. Ware (U. S. Atomic Energy Comm. Rep., *MDDC*, 1945, p. 1432) suggested the use of this reagent for the determination of uranium. As not much work appears to be on record regarding the use of chromotropic salt in colorimetric analysis, it has been thought of interest to investigate the possibility of using this reagent in analysis.

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E X P E R I M E N T A L

Validity of Beer's Law.—Confirmation of the system to Beer's law was investigated as usual using Klett-Summerson's photoelectric colorimeter, and the system was found to obey Beer's law in the range of concentration 50-200 p.p.m., when the reagent added was at least 30-50 times that of the molar concentration of the metallic ion. Some of the typical results are shown in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1

Curve A :

Conc. of uranyl sulphate = 0.0004M.
 Conc. of chromotropic salt = 0.0100M.
 Vol. of the reagent taken = 10 c.c.
 Total volume = 50 c.c.
 Filter used = 42 blue (400-450m μ).

Curve B :

Conc. of uranyl sulphate = 0.0002M.
 (Other conditions same as in curve A.)

Uranyl sulph (c.c.)

Stability of the Colour at Room Temperature.—The colour was stable at room temperature. A solution of 0.0002M in UO_2^{2+} and 0.0004M chromotropic salt at p_H 4.0 gave exactly the same optical density of 0.55 per cm at 400 m μ even after 72 hours' standing at room temperature. The optical densities were determined, using a Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer.

Influence of Temperature.—The colour intensity was found to decrease beyond 30° as may be seen below.

TABLE I

Uranyl sulphate = 0.0002 M. Chromotropic salt = 0.0004 M. p_H = 4.0.

Temp.	20°	25°	30°	35°	40°	45°
Optical density/cm (400 m μ)	0.550	0.550	0.550	0.540	0.535	0.530

Influence of p_H .—The colour was found to be stable between p_H 3.50 and 4.80 as shown below.

TABLE II

Temp. 25°. Conc. of uranyl sulphate and of chromotropic salt, same as in Table I.

p_H ...	2.60	3.00	3.50	4.20	4.80	6.30
Opt. density/cm (400 m μ)	0.300	0.450	0.550	0.550	0.550	0.700

Sensitivity.—The smallest amount of uranyl ion that can be detected by the reagent is 30 p.p.m.

Influence of Foreign Ions.—The effect of various cations and anions was studied and their approximate tolerance limit determined. The latter denotes the maximum permissible concentration of the foreign ion in the solution under investigation, which would affect the optical density by less than $\pm 2\%$. The results are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Uranyl sulphate = 0.00002M (540 p.p.m.). Chromotropic salt = 0.00040 M.
 $\mu_n = 4.0 \pm 0.50$. Temp. = 25°.

Ion.	Added as.	Conc. of ion. (p.p.m.)	Obs. change in opt. density (%).	Tolerance limit. (p.p.m.)
Ag ⁺	AgNO ₃	107	+10	11
		11	+1	
Tl ⁺	Tl ₂ SO ₄	102	-3.5	51
		51	-1.5	
Pb ²⁺	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	207	+6	35
		35	+1	
Hg ⁺	Hg ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	...	Interference at all concentrations	0
Hg ²⁺	HgCl ₂	200	+3	75
		75	+1	
Pb ³⁺	Bi oxalate	80	Turbid	...
Cu ²⁺	CuSO ₄	126	+6	21
		21	+1	
Cd ²⁺	CdCl ₂	224	+4	Large excess
		112	+2	
AsO ₃ ³⁻	H ₃ AsO ₃	123	-0.5	Do.
Sb ³⁺	Sb ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	76	Turbid	...
Sn ⁴⁺	SnCl ₄	...	Interference at all concentrations	0
Fe ³⁺	FeCl ₃	...	"	0
Fe ²⁺	Fe amm. sulph.	110	+4	55
		55	+2	
Al ³⁺	Al(NO ₃) ₃	78	+3.5	39
		39	+1.5	
Cr ³⁺	CrCl ₃	52	+4.5	10
		10	+1.5	
Mn ²⁺	MnSO ₄	108	-3.5	54
		54	-1.5	
Zn ²⁺	ZnSO ₄	130	+0.5	Large excess
Ni ²⁺	NiSO ₄	116	+0.5	Do.
Co ²⁺	CoSO ₄	116	+3.5	58
		58	+1.5	
Ba ²⁺	BaCl ₂	137	+13	10
		10	+1	
Sr ²⁺	SrCl ₂	174	+13	13
		13	+1	
Ca ²⁺	Ca(NO ₃) ₂	160	+14	10
		10	+1	
Mg ²⁺	MgSO ₄	96	+0.5	Large excess
Be ²⁺	BeSO ₄	36	+1.5	36
Th ⁴⁺	ThCl ₄	232	+3	Large excess
		116	+1.5	
Ce ³⁺	Cerous amm. sulph.	140	+3	70
		70	+1.5	

TABLE III (contd.)

Ion.	Added as.	Conc. of ion. (p.p.m.).	Obs. change in opt. density (%).	Tolerance limit. (p.p.m.).
Ce ⁴⁺	Ceric sulphate.	140 60	+4 +1.5	60
WO ₄ ²⁻	Na ₂ WO ₄	124 50	-6 -1	50
MoO ₄ ²⁻	(NH ₄) ₂ MoO ₄	...	Interferes at all concns.	0
VO ₃ ⁻	NH ₄ VO ₃	...	" "	0
Zr ⁴⁺	ZrO(NO ₃) ₂	91	+0.5	Large excess
Ti ⁴⁺	KTi oxalate	...	Interferes at all concns.	0
SeO ₄ ²⁻	K ₂ SeO ₄	143	+0.5	Large excess
TeO ₃ ²⁻	K ₂ TeO ₃	...	Interferes at all concns.	0
CO ₃ ²⁻	Na ₂ CO ₃	...	" "	0
SO ₄ ²⁻	K ₂ SO ₄	192	+0.5	Large excess
Cl ⁻	KCl	70 35	+3.5 +1.5	35
Br ⁻	KBr	160	-0.5	Large excess
I ⁻	KI	126	-0.5	" "
ClO ₃ ⁻	KClO ₃	83	-0.5	" "
BrO ₃ ⁻	KBrO ₃	128	-0.5	" "
IO ₃ ⁻	KIO ₃	175 87	+3.5 +1.5	87
F ⁻	NaF	...	Interferes at all concns.	0
SiO ₃ ²⁻	Na ₂ SiO ₃	154 26	+6 +1	26
Citrate	Na citrate	120 7	-16 -1	7
Tartrate	K tartrate	130 13	-10 -1	13
Oxalate	Amm. oxalate.	94 10	-8 -1.5	10
NO ₃ ⁻	KNO ₃	124	-0.5	Large excess
CNS ⁻	KCNS	116	-0.5	" "
PO ₄ ³⁻	Na ₂ HPO ₄	190 13	-1.5 -1.5	13
S ₂ O ₈ ²⁻	K ₂ S ₂ O ₈	192 96	-3.5 -1.5	Large excess
HCO ₃ ⁻	KHCO ₃	...	Interferes at all concns.	0
S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃	112 56	+3.5 +1.5	56
Acetate	Na acetate	...	Interferes at all concns.	0
B ₄ O ₇ ²⁻	Na ₂ B ₄ O ₇	...	" "	0

Procedure.—From a consideration of the experimental results recorded above, the following procedure for the estimation of uranium by chromotropic salt may be recommended.

For the determination of uranium in commercial materials, ores, minerals etc., a solution of the sample should be prepared and treated to separate the other elements present as usual (Snell and Snell, "Colorimetric Methods of Analysis", New York, D. Van Nostrand, Vol. I, 1928; Sandell, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", 2nd ed., Interscience Publishers, Inc., 1950). The

pure uranyl salt solution as chloride, sulphate or nitrate should be treated directly or in an aliquot portion with an excess (over 25 times the molar proportions of uranium) of a chromotropic salt solution in water. The p_H of the solution should be adjusted at 4.00 ± 0.50 . It should then be diluted to the required volume and kept for 15 minutes to attain equilibrium. The optical density can then be read at $400 m\mu$, using a cell of suitable thickness. The colour intensity can also be measured with a photoelectric colorimeter using an appropriate filter. The temperature of observation should preferably be between 20° and 30° .

Composition of the Coloured Complex.—It was thought to be of interest to determine the composition of the coloured complex formed between uranyl ion and

FIG. 2

Graphical determination of composition.

Conc. of $UO_2SO_4 = c$. Conc. of chromotropic salt = c' . $p = c'/c$. Curve A $c = 0.002M$, $p = 1$. Curve B: $c = 0.001M$, $p = 1$. Curve C: $c = 0.0005M$, $p = 1$. Curve D: $c = 0.002M$, $p = 0.5$.

disodium 1:8-dihydroxynaphthalene-3:6-disulphonate. Electrical conductance measurements were made with mixtures prepared according to Job's method of continuous variation (*Compt. rend.*, 1925, 180, 928; *Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113). The measurements were carried out using a conductivity cell of the dip type, having a cell constant of 0.132. The bridge used was L & N Kohlrausch slide wire with an audio-frequency oscillator. The solutions were always freshly prepared in conductivity water and were kept immersed in an electrically operated thermostat, maintaining a temperature of 25°, before and during the experiments. The results are represented graphically in Fig. 2, where the difference in specific conductivity (observed specific conductivity - sum of the conductivities of the constituent solutions) has been plotted against composition of the mixture.

From the curve it is evident that the components are in the ratio of 1:1 in the chelate. It was noted that the observed conductance of the mixture was in every case higher than the sum of the conductances of the components. This is probably due to the liberation of hydrogen ions as a result of chelate formation, thus,

Chelating agent (I).

Uranyl chelate (II).

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